

Spin Maintaining Spatial-Time Constraints in Equations of Action-Reaction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. June 6, 2025

Space and time are often associated with motion (e.g. $v=dx/dt$). We argued, however, in (1) that space and time variables may appear in action-reaction scenarios as in free particle quantum mechanics, where this action-reaction is described by $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. In fact, in (1) we argued that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is directly related to an interaction because if a photon interferes with a moving 2-slit apparatus, it is the momentum of the photon as seen in the rest frame of the 2-slit apparatus which determines the appropriate slit separation.

Thus, we argue that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ represents an action-reaction interaction in space with $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ representing action-reaction intervals, not dynamic ones. In the case of a photon, the two coincide. This leads to the question: What is spin?

We try to argue here that one wishes to a priori create an equation describing action-reaction, i.e. one linear in $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. This action-reaction mechanism may, however, be subject to a constraint. In particular, from special relativity one has: $E^2 = pc^2 + m^2c^4$ ((1)) for a particle with rest mass. Given $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, one may obtain E and p using $\partial/\partial t$ and $-i \partial/\partial x$, but squared terms appear in the constraint. To obtain a linear equation, one needs to linearize the quadratic expression ((1)) as Dirac did. This leads to the appearance of 4×4 matrices. The matrices linked with π , however, are composed of 2×2 Pauli matrices. These matrices act on vectors which presumably are related to space because they appear in front of π (p_x, p_y, p_z) values (or operators). The matrices are linked with the action-reaction process in that they maintain the overall constraint ((1)). Thus, spin is linked to spatial motion (albeit it in a complicated manner) linked with the action reaction-action process described by $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which does not account for the space-time constraint imposed by ((1)). The constraint itself follows from the complementarity of two frames moving at a constant velocity with respect to each other.

In the case of a photon, $E=pc$ which does not impose a space-time constraint in terms of matrices. It is known from Maxwell's equations, however, that the electric and magnetic fields oscillate as: $\text{Real}(\exp(-iEt+ipx))$. If there is a constraint on these, then one may again try to linearize it and find the matrices (spin) which impose the constraint for the $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ action-reaction process. The constraint in this case is: $\text{div}(\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E}) - \text{div}(\mathbf{j}) + \text{grad} \cdot (\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}) = 0$ where \mathbf{E} is the electric field and \mathbf{B} , the magnetic.

The overall strategy is the same for both the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particle of ((1)) and the spin 1 photon, we argue, namely that one wishes to describe the action-reaction process with a linear $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, but constraints may exist which are quadratic and force the presence of a matrix in the linear equation. . The matrices linked with p are then spatial constraint matrices which are called spin matrices. They act on vectors and presumably describe motion (perhaps angular) which may be involved in interactions just like $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. (In this case, these are interactions with a magnetic field giving the sense of spin being linked in some manner to angular motion.)

In other words, the linear equation in $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ shows the interaction physics even if more generalized quadratic equations exist which impose complementarity of frames or continuity and this is what leads to spin, we argue.

Action-Reaction

Newtonian mechanics deals with space time in terms of velocity $=dx/dt$ because interactions occur in $dx \rightarrow 0$. Even though the idea of action-reaction emerges in Newtonian mechanics, a particle with rest mass has a center-of-mass point which accelerates in each little $dx \rightarrow 0$. There is no view of an action-reaction occurring in space larger than dx or dt for this point particle. Such a picture only appears for a wave, which is a different kind of entity than a point center-of-mass. The wave, however, requires a medium which consists of particles with center-of-mass points.

Newton considered light to be a particle, but later (early 1800s) it was found to create interference patterns with a 2-slit apparatus. At first, one might consider light then to move through some kind of medium as a wave. Later in the 1800s, Maxwell found that light could be described as a self-wave created by oscillating electric and magnetic fields based on $\text{Real}(\exp(-iEt+ipx))$. We argue that this is Newton's action-reaction, but now appearing for a photon which does not move in medium. In other words, Newton's idea of a photon being a particle seems to be correct, only its action-reaction is not restricted to $dx \rightarrow 0$. In fact, the action-reaction regions in space-time are:

$$\Delta t = \hbar/E \text{ and } \Delta x = \hbar/p. \quad ((2))$$

This suggests that a particle with rest mass (which is not a self-wave) could have this same kind of action-reaction intervals if E and p are to be treated universally. Action-reaction for both a particle with rest mass and a photon involves $((2))$ and not $dx \rightarrow 0$. These intervals $((2))$ then manifest themselves through interactions with objects with built-in Δx values, like a 2-slit apparatus, etc. A point made in (1) is that $((2))$ is strictly due to interactions. In other words, a photon with p approaching a 2-slit apparatus moving with some speed means that there are two momenta in the problem and both contribute to an interaction. One cannot say that the moving 2-slit apparatus should have slit separations of \hbar/p because p is not the only momentum in the interaction. One should thus transform to the rest frame of the 2-slit apparatus to reduce the problem to a single momentum (p' of the photon) such that slit separation is now \hbar/p' .

Constraint Equations and Effects on Space for Action-Reaction

$((2))$ shows that E and p are used to describe action-reaction intervals (periodicity) in space-time. Special relativity provides equations linking E and p , such as:

$$E = pc + m_0 c^2 \quad ((3a)) \quad (\text{rest mass}) \quad \text{and} \quad E = pc \quad ((3b)) \quad (\text{photon (no rest mass)})$$

((3b)) is simply an equation linking magnitudes of E and p. It is already known from Maxwell's equations that the physical driver of action-reaction of a photon are the electric and magnetic fields which behave as real($\exp(-iEt+ipx)$) (a result which follows from Maxwell's equations). $E=pc$, however, is of the form of a wave equation with $E=\hbar$ frequency and $p=\hbar/\text{wavelength}$ and so ((3b)) also describes such action-reaction in space-time. If one considers the electric and magnetic fields, then there is an equation in addition to ((3b)), namely:

$$d/dt \text{ partial } (.5\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + .5/\mu_0 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}) + \text{grad dot } 1/\mu_0 (\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}) = 0 \quad ((4))$$

Given ((3a)), ((3b)) and ((4)), one may ask: Do they have any consequences for the action-reaction motion in space-time or are they simply magnitude equations? ((3b)), a linear equation, has already been seen to be a magnitude equation which also is consistent with wave results:((2)), but seemingly nothing more.

Let us examine ((3a)) in more detail. We ask: How does it arise? We suggest that it is a statement of the complementarity of co-ordinate systems in a rest and moving frame. In other words, a person in a moving frame thinks he/she is at rest and the other frame is moving. This does not mean that a particle at rest is the same as one that moves. A moving particle, from Newtonian mechanics, has been acted on by a force and has;

$$KE = .5mv^2 \quad \text{and} \quad p = mv \quad ((5))$$

We note that rest mass, m_0 , is inertia and represents impedance to force. In a rest frame, a rest particle has only m_0 , $KE=0$, $p=0$. In a moving frame, it has m_0 , KE and p . If these two frames are to be complementary, we ask: What equation links m_0 to m_0, KE and p ? Given that KE contains v^2 , it seems one requires p^2 which means that m_0 must also appear. If E is to be composed of m_0 and KE , then $.5mv^2$ contains v^2 , but not m_0 and so one considers a quadratic equation to first order:

$$(m_0 D + .5mv^2) (m_0 D + .5mv^2) - D p^2 \text{ approx} = m_0^2 D^2 \quad ((6))$$

D is a constant with units of velocity squared.

The quadratic form of ((6)) is based on imposing complementarity of frames (one at rest, one moving at constant $-v$.) It seems to have nothing to do with the action-reaction idea of ((2)). Nevertheless, p and E must satisfy ((6)), it is a constraint. If one tries to write an equation which is linear in E and p (in order to describe action-reaction) (as Dirac did), then one must introduce 4x4 matrices (2). The matrices which multiply p_i (p_x, p_y, p_z) contain each Pauli matrix twice. It is not enough to write an action-reaction equation for E and p (linear) using $i\hbar d/dt$ partial and $-i\hbar d/dx$ acting on the action-reaction function $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. One must also have the matrices in order to preserve the constraint ((6)). The matrices act on vectors and those associated with p_x, p_y, p_z are presumably linked to motion in space. The constraint ((6)) imposes motion of a vector (some kind of angular motion perhaps) in space. As a result, it is not only action-reaction Δx and Δt 's which exist for a particle with rest mass. There is an extra kind of motion, which

presumably is involved in interactions as the purpose of writing an equation linear in p and E is to describe the action-interaction using $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. We suggest that this is the origin of spin $\frac{1}{2}$ which holds for a particle with rest mass.

What about a photon? We argued that ((3b)) yields nothing related to an extra constraint in space. The same, however, cannot be said about ((4)). One may linearize ((4)) in order that one has an equation in $E+iB$ which both go as $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, i.e the action-reaction term. The linearization process leads to:

$E_{ijk} (\hbar \text{ complex } i) d/dx_i$ ((7)) where e_{ijk} is the Levi-Civita symbol

Here $x_i=(x,y,z)$ and e_{ijk} has i as the matrix label with jk being the entries.

Linearizing ((6)) to obtain the action reaction term $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ forces one to introduce the matrix e_{ijk} . These are presumably linked with transformations in space. A constraint leads to a kind of motion other than the action-reaction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and this extra motion should presumably be linked with interaction as $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is, we argue. We suggest that this may be part of the picture of the notion of spin for a particle with rest mass and a photon. The spin arises due to the quadratic nature of constraint equations which impose the presence of matrices when linearizing to obtain and $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ action-reaction term.

Conclusion

We have argued in previous notes (1), that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ represents a kind of action-reaction periodic motion in space-time in an interaction, i.e. $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$. We suggest that these intervals are strictly interaction based because a photon p approaching a moving 2-slit interference apparatus does not require spacing of \hbar/p to interfere, but rather \hbar/p' , where p' is the photon momentum as seen in the rest frame of the 2-slit apparatus. As a result, we suggest that both a photon and particle with rest mass interact according to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. This, however, makes no mention of spin.

We thus ask: How does spin emerge? We suggest that there exist equations linking E and p which are not linear in E and p , but rather quadratic, i.e. $EE = ppcc + \text{momocccc}$ ((B)). For the photon, one has $E=pc$ and this gives no sense of spin. The former, however, if linearized to display the action-reaction term $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ with $p \rightarrow -i\partial/\partial x$ partial and $E=i\partial/\partial t$ partial forces one to introduce matrices (as shown by Dirac). These act on vectors and the ones linked with p_x, p_y, p_z presumably act on vectors in space suggesting spatial motion. This spatial motion is required to satisfy the constraint ((B)) which is based on complementarity of frames moving at a constant relative speed, i.e. special relativity. Thus, $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ describes action-reaction, but if one wants this to be consistent with special relativity, a linear equation in $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ must describe extra spatial motion (spin motion i.e. some kind of angular motion perhaps as based on interactions with a magnetic field (Zeeman effect)). In the case of a photon, $E=pc$ shows no such matrices, but linearizing d/dt partial $(.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B) + \text{grad} \cdot 1/\mu_0 (E \times B) = 0$ does and $E+iB$ goes as $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. In this case, e_{ijk} (Levi-Civita symbol) is the matrix (i denotes matrix, jk entries). Given that these matrices are linked with constraint equations and appear when one linearizes to display the action-interaction term $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ (often called a free particle wavefunction), one expects that this motion may be involved in interactions just as

$\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is, and this is the case. Thus, spin arises as an additional interaction motion to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ to ensure that existing constraint equations are satisfied when creating a linear equation in $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ describing physical action-reaction interactions.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Newtonian Mechanics as the Driver of Special Relativity? (preprint, zenodo, 20250)
- 2 .https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dirac_equation